

Structure and properties of glass fibers insulation used in nuclear power plants.

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ABSTRACT

The basic physical properties and chemical durability of glass used for production of the NUKON glass fibrous insulation were measured. This type of glass insulation is used in nuclear power plants and its properties are important for safety reasons – namely in the case of Loss Of Coolant Accidents (LOCA). During this postulated accident, the insulation can be damaged by the jet impact and carried to the screens of the emergency systems needed to cool the reactor. In this case, the fibers can be strongly corroded by particular coolant solutions and their behavior under this environment can modify the head loss of the screens. In addition corrosion products formed during contact of insulation fibers with aggressive cooling solution can cause changes, resulting in insufficient even functionless operation of the cooling system. Therefore the chemical durability of NUKON glass fibers was tested in present work by leaching corrosion tests. The coolant solution $H_3BO_3/Na_2B_4O_7$ was used as corrosive medium. The glass dissolution was followed by atomic emission spectrometry with inductively coupled plasma (ICP - OES). The low temperature viscosity was measured by the thermomechanical analysis. The temperature dependence of viscosity was described by the Andrade viscosity equation. The glass transition temperature and the thermal expansion coefficients of glass and metastable melt were determined by the thermodilatometry. The liquidus temperature was measured in the gradient furnace by the method of the first crystal. The glass density at laboratory temperature was measured by Archimedes method. The heat capacity and glass transition characteristic were determined by DSC method.

Keywords: Glass fibres, thermal insulation, LOCA, coolant solution, physical properties, corrosion.

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